

EDGELESS: A Software Architecture for Stateful FaaS at the Edge

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ABSTRACT

EDGELESS is a serverless platform targeting edge computing that supports widely distributed deployments using heterogeneous devices. We present its components, architecture, and programming model. Our working prototype of EDGELESS enables executing lightweight functions and is already available as open-source.

KEYWORDS

serverless computing, edge computing, cloud-continuum, resource-constrained devices

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1 INTRODUCTION

Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing (EDGELESS) is a European Commission funded Horizon Europe program collaborative lasting 36 months, having started on January 1st, 2023.

EDGELESS [3] seeks to make complex FaaS application deployment both easy-to-use and flexible and applicable to different environments on an infrastructure composed of heterogeneous physical devices across the edge-cloud continuum. The project realises efficient and transparent horizontal pooling of decentralized resources by implementing the serverless concept over nodes with heterogeneous capabilities ranging from constrained resources, to specialized hardware, to traditional cloud resources. EDGELESS aims to go beyond traditional stateless serverless architectures by allowing functions to maintain and manage state information, offering a flexible and comprehensive solution for which it is easy to develop. Similar to μ Actor [5] and Cloudflare’s Durable Objects [9], EDGELESS should support instance-local state. Furthermore, it aims to

directly integrate an option to share state across multiple function instances using various SotA approaches to support different consistency models.

The EDGELESS consortium is working toward three goals. First, to design and implement an event-driven architecture able to manage applications’ **dynamic state and scalability**. This requires methods to efficiently redistribute computation from user devices and remote datacenters across a diverse infrastructure ecosystem, including edge nodes with heterogeneous computational capabilities. By leveraging an event-driven architecture, EDGELESS enables seamless communication and coordination among distributed functions. This promotes efficient handling of events and triggers, enhancing the system’s responsiveness. Second, **security and privacy concerns** are first-class considerations in EDGELESS. Encryption, access controls, and other security measures are employed to ensure that sensitive data is protected and user privacy is maintained even in a distributed edge-cloud environment. To further enhance privacy and security, EDGELESS will implement secure authentication based on Hardware Security Modules and secure stateful FaaS workflow execution in trusted enclaves [7]. Third, **longevity, sustainability, and desirability** of the EDGELESS project arises from alignment between developments and a value proposition for edge computing ecosystem actors applying the EDGELESS framework, enabling new use and business cases. On the one hand, the framework emphasises ease of use and improved developer experience by applying standard-compliant and maintainable APIs, and state-of-art tools for the different actors interacting with EDGELESS, e.g., graphical, low-code interfaces. On the other hand, EDGELESS has, from the start, adopted an open-source approach, to facilitate collaboration among developers, researchers, and industry experts, fostering innovation and sustainable development of the cutting-edge FaaS framework EDGELESS.

The EDGELESS prototype is already available,¹ able to run workflows consisting of Rust-based functions on a small set of devices.

2 EDGELESS ACTORS

We define a set of key functional roles or *actors* that interact with the framework to give rise to the architecturally significant requirements, matching feature development to value-add for specific actors, and fostering communication in framework design and development within a collaborative project. These roles are:

¹<https://github.com/edgeless-project/edgeless>

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- **Function Developer**, developing individual reusable EDGELESS functions $f(x)$, providing and managing artifacts via function repositories, and optimising performance of specific functions.
- **Application Developer**, developing end-to-end applications for EDGELESS clusters, defining application workflows, integrating applications into use cases, defining execution constraints, annotations, and resources, optimising application performance and scalability and managing application life-cycle.
- **Cluster Operator**, operating one or more EDGELESS clusters, whether on-premise, in a remote cloud environment, or in hybrid mode mixing both infrastructures, monitoring and optimising the cluster's and running applications' performance, maintaining and continuously improving EDGELESS components deployed in the cluster, and integrating new nodes and services into the cluster.

Other actors in the ecosystem are:

- **Application Business Owner**, owning the application and covering the costs of operating it on an EDGELESS cluster. Defines the functional and non-functional requirements towards the EDGELESS cluster in an end-to-end fashion.
- **Application User**, using applications running on the EDGELESS cluster in their everyday business. Provides requirements, feedback on any performance issues, and system error reports.
- **EDGELESS Developer Community**, maintaining and providing governance for the core, tools and add-ons, and community support for to the EDGELESS framework.
- **Computer Science/Systems Researchers**, making use of the EDGELESS framework to analyse and develop new serverless computing concepts, and prototyping cutting-edge features.
- **Cloud Service Provider**, providing a managed compute infrastructure to support the EDGELESS cluster and, potentially, offering a multi-tenant EDGELESS clusters as a service.

3 EDGELESS ARCHITECTURE

EDGELESS enables the execution of distributed applications on a set of heterogeneous *worker nodes*, grouped into logical *orchestration domains*, each managed by an ϵ -ORC. In addition to the worker nodes, each domain contains an ϵ -BAL that enables invocation of scalable functions from outside the domain. The set of orchestration domains operated by a single administrative entity is called a *cluster*, which is managed by an ϵ -CON. The ϵ -CON allows application developers to deploy applications packaged as *workflows*. We discuss workflows and the programming model in §4.

The EDGELESS architecture has been designed to support a broad set of deployment scenarios involving edge and cloud computing infrastructures. Figure 1 gives a high-level depiction of an example deployment that spans three clusters, one of which shows its internal structure consisting of three orchestration domains. Two of those domains are mapped to physically (and possibly geographically) separated edge computing infrastructures, while the third uses virtual resources offered by a third-party cloud provider under an Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) model. The cloud operators used by the clusters can be different.

Each orchestration domain, at the edge or in the cloud, is managed by an ϵ -ORC, but the worker nodes are different between these two cases. At the edge, the physical resources available are

Figure 1: Deployment example showing three EDGELESS clusters. The internal structure is shown only for a single cluster. Clusters are managed by the ϵ -CON, orchestration domains by an ϵ -ORC.

limited by the type, capacity, and number of nodes installed at a given site (nodes may range from embedded devices to small computers to full-fledged servers), while nodes in the cloud run inside a highly virtualized environment, using containers or virtual machines. Such a difference is transparent from the point of view of the ϵ -CON because the detailed function instance life-cycle management and optimized inter-communication happens within a single orchestration domain, mediated by the ϵ -ORC. The different ϵ -ORC instances are controlled by the ϵ -CON, which is logically centralized for each cluster. The ϵ -CON instances in the clusters may cooperate to handle workflows spanning across their respective orchestration domains, thereby achieving multi-vendor federation, under appropriate Service Level Agreements (SLAs).

Figure 2 depicts the EDGELESS architecture in more detail.

Worker Nodes: The EDGELESS worker node (Fig. 2, top left) is the application that provides the computation elements, can run in a server/virtual machine/container in the private/public cloud or hosted by a resource-constrained device at the edge. The EDGELESS worker node can support one or more function runtimes, each of which enables the execution of stateful *function instances* with their respective virtualization/isolation technologies. For instance, a node might offer both a Docker container runtime as well as a userspace VM for lightweight WebAssembly [4] functions.

Figure 2: EDGELESS architecture’s hierarchical structure, composed of *clusters*, each managed by an ϵ -CON and comprising *orchestration domains*, each managed by an ϵ -ORC, which are logical collections of *nodes*, which may host both resource providers, enabling interaction with the physical world, and function run-time environments, supporting data processing.

Function instances execute application logic only in response to asynchronous events and interact with other components exclusively by generating new events. Such events may be synchronous, i.e., blocking, or asynchronous.

Interaction with the real world occurs via *resource instances*, which are managed by the resource providers deployed on EDGELESS worker nodes. Unlike function runtimes, which are assigned instances as part of a multi-tier orchestration process that is transparent to the developers, resource providers can be addressed specifically by the application developer (§2) as they have a physical counterpart generating events (if e.g., a sensor or camera) or consuming them (if e.g., an actuator). A special resource provider illustrated in the diagram is the Data Distribution Agent (DDA), intended to bridge industrial networked devices. Nodes are managed externally via the ϵ -ORC agent.

Orchestration Domains. As noted above, EDGELESS nodes are grouped into non-overlapping orchestration domains, each containing an ϵ -ORC, an ϵ -BAL, and an instance of the observability framework. The ϵ -ORC manages the registration of EDGELESS worker nodes, during which they advertise their hardware and software capabilities (e.g., number of CPU cores, available memory, and the list of function runtimes supported), and performs the allocation of function instances to the EDGELESS worker nodes within its domain. Orchestration logic for optimising resources in the domain can be embedded within the ϵ -ORC or delegated to a third-party

optimizer, allowing the cluster operator to upgrade/experiment with different orchestration policies. In any case, orchestration decisions will be based on a real-time measurement of the system conditions, acquired from a local observability framework that collects measurements produced by the EDGELESS worker nodes during function execution, augmented by measurements from other sources, e.g., network traffic or hardware utilisation. Finally, the ϵ -BAL is used to mediate the data plane interactions between function instances assigned to different orchestration domains or clusters.

Clusters. At the top of the EDGELESS hierarchy, the orchestration domains are grouped into clusters, each managed by an ϵ -CON. The ϵ -CON is the entry point for clients that request the creation (or termination) of workflows created by the application developer (§2). The ϵ -CON also performs optimization of resource usage across clusters but at a slower rate than the ϵ -ORC and by accessing data aggregated at a coarser granularity in its cluster observability framework. This two-tier orchestration yields a high system scalability without compromising the capability of reacting fast to unpredictable events and avoiding service disruption. To enable workflows spanning multiple clusters, ϵ -CONs interact via an SLA manager that facilitates resource federation.

4 PROGRAMMING MODEL

EDGELESS Application Developers compose applications from multiple *EDGELESS Functions* by defining an *EDGELESS Workflow*.

Figure 3: Workflow with five functions and three resources.

EDGELESS Functions are the basic units of computation. As they are stateful, in line with the project’s goals, they can be viewed as actors [6] or closures. Fundamentally, they are computations invoked by events that may emit other events. They are inspired by our previous efforts [5], Erlang’s `gen_server`, and Cloudflare’s Durable Objects [9]. Each function class defines and uses a set of named outputs bound for the instances at runtime. The function classes, developed by the *Function Developers*, can be stored in a repository, and can be used in the composition of multiple applications.

Workflows link the named outputs of a function to the inputs of other functions. They specify logical instances of function classes, instantiated by one or more physical instances running on *EDGELESS* worker nodes. *EDGELESS* is inspired by concepts from Kubernetes including, e.g., Deployments and Services.

As *Functions* cannot cause any side-effects, *EDGELESS Resources* are used to interact with the outside world. As discussed above, those resources are instantiated from resource providers permanently installed on the nodes. They are configurable through their instantiation in the workflows and otherwise behave like normal functions, defining a set of named outputs, specifying their inputs, and interacting using events. They are based on μ Actor’s [5] platform actors and similar to Medusa’s [1] bridging approach.

The application developers can attach annotations to a workflow and to its logical function instances, providing additional metadata and constraints enabling the system (ϵ -CON, ϵ -ORC, *EDGELESS* worker node) to correctly and efficiently place and execute functions. There are different types of annotations: (i) quality of service requirements, (ii) hints that guide the optimization process, and (iii) business-related information such as cost limits. Figure 3 depicts a workflow comprising five functions and three resources.

4.1 Runtimes & Programming Languages

EDGELESS supports different virtualization techniques and function formats, and so nodes support multiple runtimes. An important goal of *EDGELESS* is the lightweight execution of serverless units driven by lightweight virtualization. We provide both primary native and secondary agnostic execution formats.

Native Execution. We chose Rust as the primary function format. Rust code is compiled into WebAssembly, which *EDGELESS* supports using user-space language virtual machines that can be executed on a wide range of nodes of different sizes. Those language virtual machines and their bytecodes are lightweight, enable fast start-up of the functions, and are used in state of the art deployments such as Cloudflare Workers [8]. Using such a standardised function format allows us many improvements over the state of the art in isolated execution; *EDGELESS* will add toolchains that compile functions in the network, thereby enabling native execution on the heterogeneous worker nodes. Rust has been shown to achieve secure and lightweight native execution [2].

Agnostic Execution. As some functions might rely on existing codebases and libraries, *EDGELESS* will provide a runtime enabling the execution of constrained containers on larger *EDGELESS* nodes. Naturally, many optimisations possible for the native format are not applicable to this option. However, due to the broad availability of libraries, this will be the first target to provide support for accelerators, including GPUs.

5 CONCLUSION

EDGELESS is a collaborative EU Horizon Europe funded project, designing and prototyping a serverless platform with two key contributions: support for geographically dispersed devices having wildly heterogeneous resources, and functions that share state between instances. Our existing open-source prototype already supports a lightweight virtual runtime, and will soon add support for native targets and target agnostic execution via containers. We encourage the community to investigate, deploy and collaborate as we develop the *EDGELESS* platform.

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